

THE INCREASING ROLE OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN BUSINESS OPERATIONS**Isayev S.***PhD researcher**Baku Business University**ORCID: 0009-0004-8980-9080***Abstract**

Artificial intelligence technologies are used in various fields today. The use of artificial intelligence in the implementation of business processes affects both market development and process improvement. It is widely used in analyzing customer data, managing the supply chain, and formulating marketing strategies. In addition, it is used in improving competitive strategies, building sales channels, natural language processing, and providing other predictive programs.

In this article, we have noted the role of artificial intelligence, its modern aspects, and the importance of its use in the business field. In addition, data analysis was carried out based on statistical data.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, business processes, modern technologies, economic benefits.

Introduction

Robots are now used in many areas, from automotive to aviation, from medicine to defense. The "Internet of Things" (IoT) covers everything connected to the internet, but it is increasingly used to describe objects that talk to each other. Simply put, the Internet of Things consists of connected devices, from simple sensors to smartphones and wearables. By combining these connected devices with automated systems, it is possible to collect, analyze and create an action to help someone with a specific task or to learn a process. IoT offers the opportunity to be more efficient in tasks, save time, money and often save emissions. This offers companies the opportunity to rethink the way they produce services and goods. Connected machines and objects in factories offer the potential for the fourth industrial revolution, and it is seen that new businesses will be working on IoT by 2025. The rapid development of technology and the interconnection of many things we use in our daily lives with the "internet of things"; It enables the development of elements that feed robotic technology such as artificial intelligence, speech recognition, image processing and autonomous systems and the design of faster, more powerful and smarter robots. Robot and automation systems play a key role in the competitiveness of the industry. The more intensive use of robots, assembly, robot systems and industrial image processing systems reduces production costs and achieves high quality standards. Robotic technologies are a combination of many branches of engineering and science, especially mechanical, electronic and computer engineering. In this respect, it is an interdisciplinary field. Therefore, when determining strategy and policy for robotic technologies, it is necessary to evaluate with a broad and comprehensive perspective. Today, the development of internet and mobile technologies, electronics, nanotechnology, medical developments, health and digital applications and similar mechatronic studies are accelerating. The last World Economic Forum has an important place in the Robotics and Artificial Intelligence agenda, and economists such as Roubini and Stiglitz have entered into discussions on the effects of robotics and artificial intelligence on the economy and business world. Many details are discussed in the busi-

ness world on these issues every day, and many different areas such as new business models, job descriptions, ways of doing business, business processes, financing models, workplaces and professions come to the agenda. The business world does not remain indifferent to new developments in the effects of artificial intelligence and robotic technology on business life. In the future, the change in commercial terms and the form of workforce will change the way of doing business using new technologies; this will have serious effects on daily business life. New economic models of countries and the world will be shaped by these effects. Companies around the world are investigating the capabilities of "Artificial Intelligence" (A.I.) technologies. As the cost of using artificial intelligence decreases, the scope of tasks that can be automated expands even more.

LITERATURE REVIEW**The importance of artificial intelligence in various fields today**

Artificial intelligence is an artificial operating system that is expected to exhibit high cognitive functions or autonomous behaviors specific to human intelligence, such as perception, learning, connecting multiple concepts, thinking, reasoning, problem solving, communicating, making inferences and making decisions. It can be defined as a device that perceives its environment and performs actions that maximize the chance of success in a goal. Artificial intelligence aims to enable machines to produce solutions to complex problems like humans. Artificial intelligence is generally implemented when a machine imitates the "cognitive" functions that it associates with other human minds, such as "learning" and "problem solving". Artificial Intelligence is a way for a computer, a computer-controlled robot or a software to think intelligently, similar to the human thinking system (Bharadiya, J.,2023). Artificial intelligence is achieved by examining how the human brain thinks and how people learn, decide and work while trying to solve a problem, and then using the results of this study to develop intelligent software and systems. Artificial intelligence is rapidly developing in many areas, from SIRI to personal assistant driverless vehicles that work with voice commands on devices with the iOS operating system. Artificial in-

telligence is a science and technology based on disciplines such as Computer Science, Biology, Psychology, Linguistics, Mathematics and Engineering. An important thrust of Artificial Intelligence is the development of computer functions related to human intelligence, such as reasoning, learning and problem solving. Computers are very suitable for mechanical calculations using some fixed programmed rules. These intelligent machines make things easier by performing simple monotonous operations that are not suitable for humans to do correctly and effectively. However, things get a little more difficult in complex problems. Unlike humans, computers cannot perform the processes of perceiving special situations and adapting to new situations. Artificial intelligence aims to improve the behavior of machines in such complex tasks. In addition, many artificial intelligence studies have provided us with a better understanding of our mental behaviors. Humans have interesting approaches to problem solving based on abstract thought, conscious induction and pattern recognition. Artificial intelligence can help us to understand this process by refreshing it again and then to exceed our existing capacity. Today, there are many application areas where artificial intelligence can be used. These areas can be evaluated in a wide range of applications, from military applications such as autonomous control and target detection to the entertainment world such as computer games and robotic animals. It can also be used in areas where large amounts of information must be processed, such as customer behavior and trend detection in banking, healthcare and insurance companies (Bharadiya, J. P., et.al.2023).

Modern aspects of artificial intelligence

Emerging new technologies, developments such as the Internet of Things and artificial intelligence will change the way people live, work, have fun and travel, as well as how countries and businesses interact with the world. In the future, customer demands will change and more personalized products will be demanded, as well as wider and more diverse ones. Companies that want to be successful in global competition will need to use intelligent robots that will work in production and distribution processes, artificial intelligence systems to be used in R&D, sales, marketing and management processes, and systems with the skills to enable them to exchange information with the outside world (Canhoto, A. I., Clear, F.,2020). The production of companies needs to adapt quickly to meet the needs of the market. This will be possible with Industry 4.0. With Industry 4.0, a perfection is aimed where all processes from demand to product/service development, from raw material supply to production, from production to the customer are integrated with human, machine and information technology dimensions, decision-making mechanisms are autonomous and each product or service creates instant customer-specific value. With Industry 4.0, the Internet of Things comes to life in production. With Industry 4.0, production processes in the factory will be interconnected. When devices are connected to each other, the data generated is rapidly transferred to each other with high-speed internet support through software that produces its own data for each device, and faster and more effective decisions can be

made by looking at the results obtained from the resulting data.

Artificial intelligence systems reduce the importance of cheap human-based labor while increasing the need for qualified human resources that can work with artificial intelligence systems. The development and spread of artificial intelligence systems affect every segment of society, from the education system to the business world, from managers to employees. The quality of the workforce required today may soon become unnecessary. Therefore, states need to take artificial intelligence systems into account when organizing their development plans and education systems. Even if states do not use artificial intelligence systems within their own institutions, they are affected by the increasingly widespread artificial intelligence systems. The USA, Russia, China and European countries, which are pioneers in the development of artificial intelligence systems, are making major investments in the field of artificial intelligence. The Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) has added the measurement of features such as digital literacy skills, digital citizenship, information fluency, technological literacy, creativity, innovative thinking, critical thinking, solution generation, and decision-making, which have gained importance with the development of artificial intelligence systems, to the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA). The success obtained from paper-and-pencil tests, which have a very important place in the classical education system, is being replaced by the success obtained in the virtual environment. In the transforming education system, individuals need to understand, analyze, manage, transform information in the virtual environment rather than in the real world, or synthesize new information. At this point, many cognitive features of human intelligence have been successfully created on artificial intelligence systems. However, artificial intelligence systems have not yet achieved the desired success in many other features of human intelligence such as creative thinking, creating original products, synthesizing new information, evaluating, creating visual artwork, imagining and critical thinking. Education systems are also affected by this benefit of artificial intelligence and are evolving towards raising individuals with high imagination and creativity instead of raising monotonous and robotized human types. While professions that have certain patterns and do not require creativity are easily replaced by artificial intelligence systems, it is predicted that professions that require imagination and artistic features will be done by humans for a longer time. The development of systems based on artificial intelligence has not only changed the human profile that education systems are expected to raise, but also changed the structure and functioning of education. Today, thanks to artificial intelligence applications, personalized education programs, individual performance monitoring, course content preparation, and determination of teaching models have increased the quality of education by using large data sources. With the development of artificial intelligence and technology, it has become possible to continue education independently of time and space. In addition, with the integration of artificial intelligence into education systems, options such

as free choice (flexible service), personalized learning, and project-based learning have been included in education. Today, it is seen that artificial intelligence systems are mostly used in the fields of distance education, online learning (e-learning), virtual reality, and augmented reality in education. With artificial intelligence systems, there have been changes in both the type of people the education system is expected to train and the way education operates. With this change, the most important segment that needs to adapt to the new educational goals and operating methods is educators. All stakeholders working in the education system, especially school administrators, subject teachers, and classroom teachers, need to have the skills to use artificial intelligence systems and work in harmony with artificial intelligence systems. Especially in the pandemic conditions that all countries of the world have had to deal with in the last two years; the problems experienced in compulsory distance education have shown that educational technologies and artificial intelligence should be used effectively and that artificial intelligence can be used functionally in solving the problems experienced. After this period, it is predicted that artificial intelligence studies will increase even more and will be widely used in solving problems in education.

In fact, there has been an increase in the number of studies and publications on the use of artificial intelligence systems in education. In their book titled "Artificial Intelligence in Education Promises and Implication for Teaching and Learning", Holmes, Bialik, and Fadel (2019) touched upon the fact that many governments and large companies around the world have made enormous investments in artificial intelligence studies and addressed the effects of this situation on education within the framework of the questions of "what to teach" and "how to teach". Under the heading of "what to teach students", it was emphasized that with artificial intelligence and the technologies it brings, teaching only knowledge is no longer of much importance, and instead, a more integrative perspective should be gained. In the section titled "how to teach students", the indirect and direct effects of artificial intelligence systems as an aid to teaching and as an instructor were addressed (Canhoto, A. I., Clear, F., 2020). Especially with the significant developments in the field of artificial intelligence in recent years, these technologies have become capable of making significant contributions to the field of education. While in traditional classrooms, teachers cannot deal with each student individually and completely eliminate their learning deficiencies, students' learning deficiencies can be minimized thanks to personalized educational content. Since artificial intelligence systems used in education analyze big data obtained from students, they can provide more detailed results than classical evaluation methods. While the use of artificial intelligence-based systems provides many advantages in terms of the quality of education, a system where teachers are out of the picture and only based on artificial intelligence will not be functional. Because although artificial intelligence systems act like personal teachers, they can sometimes give wrong results for more specific situations because they are based on big data analysis (Dietzmann, C., Alt, R., 2020).

The role of artificial intelligence in businesses today

In the modern business environment, more and more new technologies are emerging that transform traditional methods of work and management. Artificial intelligence (AI) is one of these technologies, which is already actively used in business analysis and plays an important role in shaping the development strategy of organizations, especially in the context of digital transformation. What does AI give to business analysis:

1) Big Data analysis. AI allows you to process large volumes of data faster and more efficiently than a person, as well as find hidden dependencies and patterns in data. This allows companies to make more informed decisions, reduce costs and improve the quality of products and services. In addition, the use of AI in big data processing is also becoming relevant in connection with the development of new technologies, such as the Internet of Things (IoT), when a large number of devices collect data in real time. The use of AI in such conditions allows companies to quickly analyze data and make prompt decisions. A literature review on the topic shows that the use of AI in big data processing has broad prospects and is already being used in various industries. For example, a study published in the Harvard Business Review claims that AI can significantly speed up the processing of large amounts of data and reduce the cost of processing information several times. It is also noted that AI can help highlight hidden patterns and dependencies in data that may not be noticeable during manual data processing. Another study published in the journal Nature explored the possibilities of using AI to analyze medical data. The authors of the study claim that AI can help detect early symptoms of diseases and offer the most effective treatment, which can save millions of lives (Enholm, I. M., et.al. 2022). However, the literature also notes some problems associated with the use of AI in big data processing. For example, a study published in the journal Communications of the ACM claims that AI can lead to errors due to the fact that machine learning algorithms cannot always take into account the context and can give incorrect decisions. In general, the literature review shows that the use of AI in big data processing has many promises, but is also associated with some problems that require further research. It is important to develop more advanced machine learning algorithms and establish appropriate ethical standards and legislation to ensure the proper use of AI in big data processing. Research results show that the use of AI in big data processing can significantly speed up the data analysis process and increase the accuracy of results (Feuerriegel, S., et.al. 2022). For example, a study published in PLOS ONE used machine learning algorithms to analyze large volumes of medical data. The study found that the use of AI allows you to identify more accurate patterns in the data, which can help develop more effective treatments. Also, a study published in Expert Systems with Applications applied deep learning algorithms to analyze data in the banking sector. The study found that the use of AI can reduce data processing costs and increase the accuracy of forecasts, which can help banks make more informed decisions and improve the quality of services (Jain, R., 2023).

2) Automation of processes. The use of AI allows you to automate many processes that previously required significant time and resources. For example, AI can automatically collect information from various sources, analyze it and issue ready-made reports. This happens much faster than if a person were to manually process all this information. Business process automation with AI is the use of machine learning algorithms and other AI techniques to perform tasks that were previously performed by humans. AI can process large amounts of data, make decisions based on the analysis of information, and perform tasks more efficiently and accurately than is possible for a human (Kolos, A. M., 2024).

Prospects of Business Process Automation with AI:

- A) Increased efficiency,
- B) Reduced costs,
- C) Improved quality and accuracy,
- D) Accelerated decision making,

Technologies and methods:

A) Machine learning is an artificial intelligence technique that enables computer systems to learn and improve based on experience and data. In the context of business process automation, machine learning can be used to create models and algorithms that can automatically analyze data, predict trends, optimize processes, and make decisions (La Torre, D., et.al. 2023).

B) Natural Language Processing (NLP) is a technology that enables computer systems to understand and process natural language, such as text or speech. In business process automation, NLP can be used to automatically analyze and classify text data, create chatbots to communicate with customers, provide automatic translation, and many other tasks.

C) Computer vision is a technology that enables computer systems to see and analyze images and videos. In business process automation, computer vision can be used for automatic object recognition, defect detection, quality control, and many other tasks involving visual data processing.

D) Robotics is a field of artificial intelligence that deals with the creation and programming of robots. In business process automation, robotics can be used to automatically perform physical tasks such as assembly, packaging, delivery, and other operations that were previously performed manually (Lopes da Costa, R., et.al. 2019).

Automatic decision making is an artificial intelligence method that enables computer systems to make decisions based on data analysis and pre-set rules. In business process automation, automatic decision making can be used to optimize processes, automatically manage resources, and make operational decisions in real time (Wright, S. A., Schultz, A. E., 2018).

3) Forecast accuracy. Machine learning algorithms can analyze thousands of metrics to make an accurate forecast. It takes a lot of time for a person to evaluate such an array of information, and the conclusions are not always correct. The main difference between AI forecasting and traditional forecasting is that machine learning can analyze all business indicators. It finds patterns that are invisible to humans. The decision made by artificial intelligence is completely autonomous. It

can be used to create new forecasts. Demand forecasting allows companies to purchase or manufacture the required amount of products to avoid shortages or excesses in the warehouse, as well as to meet customer needs. Forecasting the growth of a company's model (sales to income ratio) helps develop a business strategy. Based on data on future growth, companies make decisions on spending, resource allocation, etc. With the help of artificial intelligence, financial companies predict fraudulent transactions and take measures to prevent them. The use of "smart" technologies also allows predicting the value of real estate, taking into account the location of objects and historical prices. Manufacturers use AI to reduce downtime and improve production efficiency. Smart forecasting allows you to plan maintenance and optimize deliveries. AI-based forecasting helps predict risks, detect fraudulent schemes, manage personal rates, develop a marketing strategy and expand the customer base. Programs predict leads with the highest probability of conversion. They also help set prices for products and predict the likelihood of adverse situations during delivery, which allows you to conclude an insurance contract on time (Paliwal, M., et.al. 2021).

4) Strategy development. Developing a business strategy using artificial intelligence includes the following stages: A) Primary analytics. At this stage, companies compare data on dashboards and try to find patterns. It is important to collect and systematize data from all departments, as they will be useful at the second stage. They can be placed in one program, and the next new ones can be entered into the same space, so that the AI solution implemented later analyzes the entire array of information and takes into account the information of different departments.

B) Diagnostics and detection of approximate problems and drivers. This step is necessary to select tools. You can assemble a team of developers and analysts to check how real and serious the identified problems are, and also take a "test" project and check on it how much AI solutions will help it (Soni, N., et.al. 2018). Colleagues from both blocks are needed here to look at the situation comprehensively and assess the need and technical feasibility of implementing the system, its potential effectiveness.

C) Predictive analytics. At this stage, it is important to understand how to develop existing processes with the help of an AI solution and build a system. It is important to understand how we will develop existing processes with the help of an AI solution and build a system. Therefore, all leaders of the directions will be useful to control the options for strategic decisions that the neural network will offer.

5) Personalization. One of the areas of application of AI in business analysis is the personalization of services and products for end customers (Ransbotham, S., et.al. 2018).

METHODOLOGY

In our study, an analysis of statistical figures will be conducted to determine the relationship between artificial intelligence and business operations. In this direction, a statistical assessment will be conducted based on official statistical sources to determine the role of

artificial intelligence today, investments made in artificial intelligence, its impact on business operations, and

future aspects of business operations with artificial intelligence in the future.

Graph 1. Artificial intelligence market size, 2022-2033, billion dollars

Source: <https://www.precedenceresearch.com/artificial-intelligence-for-it-operations-platform-market>

The graph shows the total market size of artificial intelligence from 2022 to 2033. The expansion of the artificial intelligence market has led to an increase in its role in business operations, and the development of digital technologies has become an important factor in the

integration of artificial intelligence into business operations. Accordingly, it is noted that it will exceed \$ 20 billion in 2026, \$ 40 billion in 2030, and \$ 50 billion the following year. The main reason for this is the widespread use of artificial intelligence in various areas of organization today, including business.

Fig 1. Potential impact of generative artificial intelligence (AI) on productivity worldwide in 2023, by business functions(in billion U.S. dollars)

Source: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1446250/worldwide-artificial-intelligence-impact-by-business-function/#>

The figure shows the potential impact of AI on productivity across various business functions in 2023. Based on the figure, we can see that AI was used most in marketing and sales. The total volume of business

operations in marketing, information technology and sales was recorded at a maximum value of \$1.2 trillion. It was also widely used in supply chain, customer operations, strategy and finance. However, among

these, supply chain ranked high at approximately \$580 billion. The lowest figure was in talent and organization, as well as corporate IT.

Artificial intelligence allows you to analyze the preferences, interests, and behavior of merchants in order to offer them the most suitable products or services. This helps to strengthen customer loyalty and increase sales. In conclusion, the use of artificial intelligence in

business analysis provides many advantages and opens up new opportunities for companies. Despite its name, AI rather acts as an accelerator that improves the work of people, rather than replacing them. In this relationship, the key issue is the effective cooperation between humans and artificial intelligence. It is the combination of these two resources that will allow achieving the highest efficiency of business analysis.

Graph 2. Revenues generated by businesses using AI, 2016-2025, million dollars

Source: Prepared by the author himself as a result of research

The diagram shows the revenue growth of enterprises using artificial intelligence from 2016 to 2025. Based on the figures and the general trend, it is clear that the amount has increased over time. In 2016, it was \$357.89 million, and in 2020, this figure is expected to

reach \$4806.3 million, and by the end of 2025, this figure is expected to reach \$31256.92 million. This figure is expected to increase, especially with the use of process automation, chatbots and other tools such as analytics programs.

Fig 2. Levels of business adoption of artificial intelligence (AI) according to CEOs and CMOs worldwide as of November 2023, by share

Source: <https://www.statista.com/statistics/1261607/business-adoption-ai-ceo-cmo/>

The chart shows the level of AI adoption among global CEOs and CMOs as of November 2023. 32% of CMOs have already integrated AI into their business operations, compared to 23% of CEOs. A large portion of both groups (43% of CEOs and 39% of CMOs) are

still exploring the adoption of AI. Only a small portion plan to integrate AI immediately. While AI is expanding, some organizations are still in the process of exploring the benefits of AI.

Graph 3. Directions of using artificial intelligence in businesses

Source: Prepared by the author himself as a result of research

The diagram shows the integration directions of artificial intelligence and their percentages. Thus, data security is in first place with 71%, while cybersecurity is in second place with 69%. This figure is 69% in social media analysis, chatbots and business strategies. Robotization was 62%, Natural language processing was 60% and other services were 43%.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Since artificial intelligence systems are developing and spreading very rapidly today, it is clear that standing against artificial intelligence will be an unnecessary endeavor at this point. Instead of competing with artificial intelligence systems, people should focus on developing their skills in using and managing them.

From the smallest units of the states to the highest units, from the oldest individuals of the society to the youngest individuals, they need to be trained so that they can understand and adapt to artificial intelligence systems. In addition, establishing control and audit mechanisms to prevent the misuse of artificial intelligence systems will be beneficial in terms of carrying out the studies more healthily. In addition to all these, the use of artificial intelligence, especially in the field of education, will provide practicality in many areas and will make important contributions. Adaptation to the effects of artificial intelligence systems on all scientific fields and society can only be achieved through the education system. On the other hand, the education system also benefits from artificial intelligence systems while preparing individuals for the change caused by artificial intelligence.

CONCLUSION

In general, using artificial intelligence technologies, marketers do not spend as much time on analysis and preparation of reports as before. They use new technologies to more optimally determine the content and strategies of the campaign they will present. Thus, through artificial intelligence, marketers can see the current situation from a wider perspective and determine their strategies accordingly. Businesses use augmented reality technology to sell their products in a more interactive way. Augmented reality is the creation of a physical appearance of the real-world environment and its contents by enriching it with sound, image, graphics, etc. information by a computer. This technology can also be defined as the placement of virtual objects on real objects using the object recognition feature of devices. The use of augmented reality allows companies to move to a higher level in their communication with customers. As an example, we can mention product testing. One of the behaviors that is often seen in consumer purchasing habits is testing the product before buying it. Augmented reality brings products closer to the buying audience by providing the closest possible view to reality. For example, a consumer can see how a dress will fit them or how a favorite sofa will look in the living room without going to the store through this technology. A study conducted in the United States (US Virtual and Augmented Reality Users 2020) found that 72.8 million people in this country used augmented reality at least once a month in 2019. Considering the benefits of augmented reality technology, investments in this field are also increasing year by year. Thus, while global spending on augmented reality technology was \$11 billion in 2017, it is expected to reach \$22.8 billion in 2025, and by 2030 this figure will increase 15 times to \$342 billion. Thus, it is important for businesses to determine consumer preferences in order to increase sales volume. Today, smartphones, social media, and connected devices generate more information than ever before. Businesses are using artificial intelligence tools to transform this information into valuable products that can be sold. There are many platforms used in this field. Examples of these

include: Invoca, Appier, Lexalytics, Netbase, Airpr, Persado, etc. platforms.

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